

Modular programme for Education and Training

YOUTH SPORT COACH

M#2 Principles of Coaching Children

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Website: <https://edupass-project.eu/>

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Six Core Modules of EduPASS Modular Programme for Education and Training for Youth Sport Coach

The following are the proposed six core modules for Youth Sport Coaches education and training programmes that were developed as part of the EduPASS Erasmus+ Project. The core modules should be seen as a flexible reference point which require contextual adaptation. Those individuals and/or organisations using the six core modules to develop learning opportunities for Youth Sport Coaches should use the knowledge of their specific context to customise the modules to fit their needs, resources and objectives.

Each of the six EduPASS core modules proposed for YSC education and training programmes was developed building on the knowledge and insights, which can be found in the [European Coaching Children Curriculum \(ECCC\)](#). The ECCC, in turn, is built around the Primary Functions of the Coach as described in the European Sport Coaching Framework (2017) ([CoachLearn | European Sport Coaching Framework](#)) and the [International Sport Coaching Framework \(2013\)](#).

The respective module number and order in which the modules are presented in the table below do not indicate that modules must be introduced in this specific order, when implementing a Youth Sport Coach education and training programme. Rather the numbers simply serve as distinct denominators to help identify specific modules in the overall context of the EduPASS YSC education and training programme.

Core Module Overview

No	Module Title	Description
1	Daily Physical Activity and Sport & Motor Skills Assessment	<p>Daily physical activity, Movement, Play, and Sports (PAMPS) has many benefits for children – physically, psychologically, emotionally and cognitively. In this context, the development of physical literacy of each child is essential.</p> <p>Awareness of trends in children’s participation levels, physical activity guidelines, the needs and wants of children and how to engage with children in age-appropriate ways, will assist the coach.</p> <p>Knowledge on the growth and development of children in all aspects (socially, physically, emotionally and cognitively) is essential.</p> <p>This should be underpinned by the coach’s personal values and beliefs about the role of PAMPS for children and young people and about what constitutes ‘good practice’ (their coaching philosophy).</p> <p>To support individual children and to develop programmes based on their needs, the ability to assess motor skills will guide this work.</p>

<p>2</p>	<p>Principles of Coaching Children</p>	<p>The principles of good coaching practice with children should be used by the Youth Sport Coach (YSC). These form the basis for the 10 principles of the ICOACHKIDS Pledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Principle 1 — Be child-centred • Principle 2 — Be holistic • Principle 3 — Be inclusive • Principle 4 — Make it fun and safe • Principle 5 — Prioritise the love for sport over learning sport • Principle 6 — Focus on foundational skills • Principle 7 — Engage parents positively • Principle 8 — Plan progressive programmes • Principle 9 — Use difference methods to enhance learning • Principle 10 — Use competition in a developmental way <p>The YSC develops a programme based on their needs and the stage of development of children, based on the principles of coaching children.</p> <p>The YSC seeks to optimise the environment in which the programme occurs. The ability to navigate this can be guided by the Youth Sport Compass. The compass has 4 pillars – Developmental, Motivational, Caring and Social Safety – which can guide the YSC.</p> <p>The organisational and social context of the programme, including the participants (children/parents/club) should be taken into account.</p>
<p>3</p>	<p>Inclusive Coaching / Safeguarding</p>	<p>The Youth Sport Coach builds positive and effective relationships and works with a group of participants (children, club, school, parents, federation and other levels) and takes responsibility for the realisation of the common and individual objectives, and to achieve the programme and club goals. Hearing ‘the Voice’ of each child is an important component of this.</p> <p>Safeguarding and child protection must underpin the establishment of a safe environment for children in sport.</p>
<p>4</p>	<p>Fundamental Movement Skills and Play</p>	<p>Children should develop foundational motor skills to underpin their love of being active and to have the competence to engage in a range of activities. The development of fundamental movement (balance, agility, coordination, speed) and motor skills (run, move, jump, land, throw, catch, kick, etc) is essential, and is supported by contexts that engage children in fundamental play activities.</p>
<p>5</p>	<p>Hands-on Coaching</p>	<p>The Youth Sport Coach needs to develop their personal coaching skills and coaching tools. These include - introducing activities, demonstration, set-up and stand back, questioning and listening, feedback and reflection.</p> <p>Based on the principles of coaching children, inclusive coaching, and development of fundamental motor skills, the YSC needs to plan and organise suitable and challenging practices and attendance at events, using effective pedagogy and methodology, to promote the learning and improvement of children.</p>

		<p>The development of personal coaching skills and the planning of practices/events need to be practiced both with peers and in experiential learning situations with children. Thus, the aim of this module is to help craft safe learning experiences where “coaches learn how to coach by coaching”. Those hands-on coaching experiences enable coach learners to prepare coaching, engage in, and have an opportunity to receive feedback and engage in self-reflection about their coaching practice.</p>
<p>6</p>	<p>Plan, Reflect and Learn</p>	<p>The environment, which Youth Sport Coaches contribute to, can be welcoming and inclusive to all children. Individual coaches can provide this in their personal coaching and can also contribute to a club / school having child-centred values and policies. The Youth Sport Coach will examine their personal coaching philosophy and a means to support a club / school to adopt child-centred values and policies.</p> <p>Reflection on practice has been identified as a key means of learning and ongoing development for coaches. This can be supported by engaging with others and to a club / school being a learning environment for coaches (as well as children). Reflection is a learned skill and the Youth Sport Coach will reflect on their practice individually, with co-coaches and with a mentor.</p>

Youth Sport Coach – Programme Outcomes

The action-oriented outcomes and results for coaches for the complete module programme for Education and Training are presented below. The outcomes have been adapted from the [European Sport Coaching Framework](#) (Human Kinetics, 2017).

	The Youth Sport Coach in training will have taken the first steps towards being able to:
Coaching Vision and Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a suitable vision for the programme relevant to the participants (and in line with institutional priorities) • Make effective and informed decisions relating to the planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of mid- to long-term programmes (of practice and competition) based on (institutional and) participant needs • Encourage adopting sustainable, life-long engagement in PAMPS / Daily PA
Shape the Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to identify, reflect on and challenge prevailing beliefs, values and assumptions within the coaching environment to establish a suitable culture for PAMPS • Know how to create an environment where all children feel safe and included • Know about and be able to identify potential dangers for children in sport • Contribute to crafting and upholding a coaching environment / club / school that has child-centred values and policies • Build a community of practice and contribute to the on-going learning of other coaches and that where they coach is a learning environment for coaches.
Building Positive Relationships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to establish and maintain an ethical, effective, inclusive and empathetic relationship with children and other stakeholders (e.g., parents) • Understand how to appreciate physical, mental and cultural diversity in children and adapt PAMPS practice accordingly
Coaching Practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to conduct (comprehensive) needs analyses (assessments) for individual children (and/or teams) in order to design and deliver tailored coaching programmes, taking into account children needs and capabilities (in the context of wider programmes, curricula, policies and targets) • Understand how to select, design and justify appropriate pedagogy, practice and communication methods to facilitate the short, medium and long-term learning needs of children • Understand the core elements of multi skills or of their chosen sport(s) at the key stages of child development • Know how to deliver a series of coaching sessions in the context of medium term and long term planned programmes of practice and competition using a

	wide range of appropriate learning modes for children and coaching behaviours
Decision Making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand how to conduct an informed analysis of own performance and of the performance of children towards ensuring continuous progress and improvement • Understand how to make good in-action and post-action decisions to increase the chances of reaching short-, mid- and long-term objectives • Apply knowledge of fundamentals of movement, fundamental movement skills and fundamental game skills to create practices that lead to short-term and long-term learning, including play • Apply knowledge of motor skill development for children and youth, including the stages/phases of skill development and the impact of growth and maturation
Coaching Review and Reflection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to conduct an insightful analysis of coaching practice to make informed judgements relating to the efficacy of the learning environment established • Reflect on their personal coaching knowledge, skills, attitudes, values, and practice, with the aim of continuously improving • Continuously build and engage with a network of coaches / coach developers to keep reviewing and building personal best-practices in coaching children, seeking supervised hands-on coaching contexts

Module Structure

Core Module	Principles of Coaching Children
Module Number	2
Core Module Aim	<p>The aim of the core module is to achieve: Examine the knowledge about children, their growth and development and the implications for the organisation and coaching of sport including children’s knowledge, skills, attitudes and values in physical activities.</p>
Module Description	<p>The “Principles of Good Coaching Practice with Children” should be used by the coach. These form the basis for the 10 principles of the ICOACHKIDS Pledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Principle 1—Be child-centred Principle 2—Be holistic Principle 3—Be inclusive Principle 4—Make it fun and safe Principle 5—Prioritise the love for sport over learning sport Principle 6—Focus on foundational skills Principle 7—Engage parents positively Principle 8—Plan progressive programmes Principle 9—Use difference methods to enhance learning Principle 10—Use competition in a developmental way <p>The module will examine the theoretical basis for the 10 principles and consider what they mean in practice when coaching children.</p> <p>A navigational tool, the Youth Sport Compass, will be used to assist the coach to consider the development, motivation, caring and safe sport environments for the children they coach.</p> <p>The coach should be able to develop a programme based on the needs and stage of development of children, based on the principles of coaching children.</p> <p>The organisational and social context of the programme, including the participants (children/parents/club) should be taken into account.</p>
Module Duration	30 hours (including 7 hours of Self-Directed Learning)
Facilities and Equipment	Seminar room and gym
Methodology	Class based lectures / workshops to consider the 10 child-centred principles and the Youth Sport Compass and the knowledge / theories behind them.

	<p>The module will also include field-based practical sessions, during which coaches will be involved in experiencing practical coaching skills (peer-coaching), to examine the practical implications and application of the knowledge / theories, when coaching children.</p> <p>Self-directed learning and the completion and presentation of case studies will also be included.</p>
Coaching Materials	Logbook / reflection book
Suggested Readings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ICOACHKIDS Pledge can be accessed here - ICOACHKIDS Pledge. • The coach learner guides for Chapters 1- 4 of the ICOACHKIDS Course 2 relate to the knowledge about children, their growth and development and the implications for the organisation and coaching of sport. COURSE 2: Child-Centred Coaching and Physical Literacy (icoachkids.org) • European Sport Coaching Framework • ICOACHKIDS-Literature-Review-Web-Version-FINAL-Dec-2017.pdf (assets-servd.host) • Videos - ICK Pledge – 10 Golden Principles: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=t8UikQNO2R8 Youth Sport Compass: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=83McfP3FUOk
Evaluation	EduPASS Evaluation Tool for Youth Sport Coach Programmes
<p>Module structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 courses)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Course 2.1: ICOACHKIDS Pledge – 10 Principles of Coaching Children <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 2h Workshop/Practical Experience ○ 2h Self-Directed Working hours • Course 2.2: Child Development and Implications for Physical Activity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 2 h Workshop/Practical Experience ○ 2 h Self-Directed Working hours • Course 2.3: Motivating Children in Sport <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 2 h Workshop/Practical Experience ○ 2 h Self-Directed Working hours • Course 2.4: Setting a Caring Environment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 2 h Workshop/Practical Experience ○ 2 h Self-Directed Working hours • Course 2.5: Safe Sport Climate for Children <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 2 h Workshop/Practical Experience ○ 2 h Self-Directed Working hours

<p>Learning outcomes <i>for Youth Sport Coaches</i></p>	<p>The module will enable the Youth Sport Coach in training to build the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values) which serve as a foundation when engaging with the children they coach:</p>	
	<p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • about children’s interests & preferences • of basic motor development • regarding group dynamics & social interaction • benefits of learner-centred approaches • basic pedagogical principles • pertaining to the role of play & exploration of activities in informal PAMPS 	<p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to promote fun and enjoyment • Communication skills • Conflict management skills • Cooperation skills • Teaching / pedagogical skills • Motivational skills • Leadership skills • Active Listening skills
	<p>Attitudes: <i>YSCs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging with children they coach:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respecting children’s needs and interests • Enthusiasm • Creativity • Cooperation • Motivation • Fun and enjoyment • Empathy • Patience 	<p>Values: <i>YSCs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging with children they coach:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respect • Fair play • Cooperation • Empathy • Inclusion • Honesty • Fun & enjoyment
<p>Learning outcomes <i>for children/learners</i></p>	<p>The module will enable the Youth Sport Coach in training to support the children they coach to develop the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values)</p>	
	<p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • awareness about their interests & preferences • regarding basic motor development processes • fundamentals of social interaction • benefits of play & exploration of activities in PAMPS 	<p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fun and enjoyment • Communication skills • Cooperation skills • Motivation skills • Active Listening skills
	<p>Attitudes:</p>	<p>Values:</p>

	<p><i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respecting other children’s needs and interests • Enthusiasm • Creativity • Cooperation • Fun and enjoyment • Empathy • Patience 	<p><i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respect • Fair play • Cooperation • Empathy • Inclusion • Honesty
<p>Connection to other Core Module</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Module 3: Inclusive Coaching / Safeguarding • Module 5: Hands-on Coaching 	

Course Structure

Course Title	ICOACHKIDS Pledge – 10 Principles of Coaching Children		
Course Number	2.1		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>The principles of good coaching practice with children should be used by the coach. These form the basis for the 10 principles of the ICOACHKIDS Pledge:</p> <p>Principle 1—Be child-centred Principle 2—Be holistic Principle 3—Be inclusive Principle 4—Make it fun and safe Principle 5—Prioritise the love for sport over learning sport Principle 6—Focus on foundational skills Principle 7—Engage parents positively Principle 8—Plan progressive programmes Principle 9—Use difference methods to enhance learning Principle 10—Use competition in a developmental way</p> <p>The coach develops a programme based on their needs and stage of development of children, based on the principles of coaching children.</p>		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L / W	2 h	Teaching Unit 1: ICK Pledge – The 10 Golden Principles of Coaching Children
	W / PE	2 h	Teaching Unit 2: Practical Implications of Applying the 10 Principles
	SDL	2 h	Teaching Unit 3: Complete the study guide for ICK MOOC 1 and Essential Readings
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Child-centred sport, addressing the needs of the whole-child, including all children and engaging parents Setting an environment that is fun and safe for children and focusses on each child developing a love of being active Foundational skills for children – cognitive, affective and psychomotor Progressive programmes and different learning methods Using competition in a developmental way 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Peer-coaching sessions that are planned, delivered and evaluated by the students. Each student should explain which key principles are applied in their session. The evaluation should affirm if the principles were applied, and what else could be done to further include the principles. 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developing Effective Environments For Youth Sport, Chapter 1: The Role of the Children’s Coach, Section3, page 33-38 - Chapter-1-The-Role-of-the-Childrens-Sport-Coach-Study-Guide.pdf (assets-servd.host) 	

Course Title	Child Development and Implications for Physical Activity		
Course Number	2.2		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>The YSC in training will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand what physical literacy is. • Understand the multi-layered and progressive nature of human development. • Explore key developmental outcomes across different developmental areas and stages of development. • Understand implications for practice and explore what this may look like in their coaching environments and sessions. 		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L / W	2 h	Teaching Unit 1: Understanding Physical Literacy
	W / PE	2 h	Teaching Unit 2: Child Development – Social, Physical, Emotional and Cognitive (SPEC)
	SDL	2 h	Teaching Unit 3: Complete the study guide for ICK MOOC 2, Chapter 3 and Essential Readings
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of Physical Literacy • The domains of physical literacy – cognitive, affective and psychomotor • The individual’s physical literacy journey • How and where children can develop physical literacy • Using physical literacy as a lens when coaching children 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The social development of children – learning to act with others and the world around them • The physical development of children – general growth, chronological age, biological age (puberty and growth spurt) • The emotional development of children – awareness of self (feelings), talking about emotions (language and vocabulary), understanding / controlling emotions, empathy, dealing with authority / conflict • The cognitive development of children – thinking, problem solving, forming judgements, decision making and learning • Creating a developmental climate – role model, interaction, learning activities to suit individuals, coaching tools – question, listening, self-referenced (ipsative) feedback 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study guide for ICK MOOC 2: Child-Centred Coaching and Physical Literacy, Chapter 3: How Children Grow and Develop - Chapter-1-The-Role-of-the-Childrens-Sport-Coach-Study-Guide.pdf (assets-servd.host) 	

Course Title	Motivating Children in Sport		
Course Number	2.3		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>The YSC in training will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> embrace the idea that, what children and young people want and need from sport, varies as a function of age and development. Understand key motivational theories and what they mean to coaching children. 		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L / W	2 h	Teaching Unit 1: Understanding the Psycho-Social Development of Children
	L / W	2 h	Teaching Unit 2: Motivating Children in Sport
	SDL	1 h	Teaching Unit 3: Complete MOOC 1, Developing Effective Environments for Youth Sport, Chapter 4
	SDL	1 h	Teaching Unit 4: Complete MOOC 2: Child-Centred Coaching and Physical Literacy, Chapter 1: Motivating Children in Sport
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The development of Self Emotional, social, cognitive and moral development Life skills development 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Self-determination – competence, autonomy and belonging Achievement goals – mastery orientation and performance orientation The coach-athlete relationship 	
	TU 3	<p>MOOC 1: Developing Effective Environments for Youth Sport , Chapter 4: What sport means for children and what it can do for their personal development Chapter-4-What-sport-means-for-children-and-what-it-can-do-for-their-personal-development-Study-Guide.pdf (assets-servd.host)</p>	
	TU 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MOOC 2: Child-Centred Coaching & Physical Literacy, Chapter 1: Motivating Children in Sport Chapter-1-Motivation-in-Sport-Study-Guide.pdf (assets-servd.host) 	

Course Title	Setting a Caring Environment		
Course Number	2.4		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>The YSC in training will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe what a caring climate is • Understand the importance of building effective relationships with children and their parents • Identify the key factors of being a caring coach. 		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L / W	2 h	Teaching Unit 1: Creating a Caring Climate
	W / PE	2 h	Teaching Unit 2: Practically Setting up a Caring Climate
	SDL	2 h	Teaching Unit 3: Complete the study guide for ICK MOOC 1, Chapter 5 and Essential Readings
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify what is a caring climate • Building effective relationships with children and parents • Being an inclusive coach 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peer-coaching sessions that are planned, delivered and evaluated by the students. Each student should explain how a caring climate is applied in their session. The evaluation should affirm if the caring climate was applied and how, and what else could be done to further develop the caring climate. 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MOOC 1, Developing Effective Environments for Youth Sport, Chapter 5: Creating a Pedagogical Climate https://faded-duck.files.svdcdn.com/production/Chapter-5-What-are-the-ingredients-of-a-positive-sport-environment-Study-Guide.pdf?dm=1710927122 	

Course Title	Safe Sport Climate for Children		
Course Number	2.5		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>The YSC in training will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe what a safe sport climate is • Understand the importance of a child-centred coaching philosophy • Understand coaching behaviours and skills that support a safe sport climate. 		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L / W	2 h	Teaching Unit 1: Creating a Safe Sport Climate
	L/ W	2 h	Teaching Unit 2: Developing a Child-Centred Coaching Philosophy
	SDL	2 h	Teaching Unit 3: Complete the study guide for ICK MOOC 1, Chapter 2 and Essential Readings
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define a Safe Sport Climate – where children feel safe to learn, have opportunities to learn and improve and where children feel the coach cares for them • Peer-coaching sessions that are planned, delivered and evaluated by the students. Each student should explain how a safe sport climate is applied in their session. The evaluation should affirm if the safe sport climate was applied and how, and what else could be done to further develop the safe sport climate. 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing a Child-Centred Coaching Philosophy • Using your coaching tools to reflect a coaching philosophy – how you communicate and what you do in coaching session and at competition 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MOOC 1: Developing Effective Environments for Youth Sport, Chapter 2: What is a Coaching Philosophy and Why it is Beneficial to be Clear About Yours Chapter-2-What-is-a-coaching-philosophy-and-why-it-is-beneficial-to-be-clear-about-yours-Study-Guide.pdf (assets-servd.host) 	